

List of works retrieved for analysis in the paper ‘UJIIndoorLoc Dataset A Retrospective Analysis after 10 Years of Usage’

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Abstract

This document provides the list of conference and journal papers that have cited, referenced and used the UJIIndoorLoc dataset [1], [2]. This list is part of the work presented at the International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation 2025, which took place in Tampere, Finland [3].

Index Terms

Fingerprinting; Wi-Fi; Indoor Positioning; Dataset; Open Research Data

TABLE I
LIST OF 283 WORKS PUBLISHED IN 2015–2024 CITING AND USING THE UJIINDOORLOC EMPIRICALLY [1], [2]

Manuscript title	Year	Ref.
A comparative study on machine learning algorithms for indoor positioning	2015	[4]
Comprehensive analysis of distance and similarity measures for Wi-Fi fingerprinting indoor positioning systems	2015	[5]
Enhancing integrated indoor/outdoor mobility in a smart campus	2015	[6]
Evaluating indoor localization solutions in large environments through competitive benchmarking: The EvAAL-ETRI competition	2015	[7]
Fingerprint calibrated centroid and scalar product correlation RSSI positioning in large environments	2015	[8]
Localization performance quantification by conditional entropy	2015	[9]
Mean mutual information of probabilistic wi-fi localization	2015	[10]
POI estimation method with incremental update based on smartphones	2015	[11]
Wi-Fi fingerprinting in the real world - RTLS@UM at the EvAAL competition	2015	[12]
A calibration-free crowdsourcing-based indoor localization solution	2016	[13]
A mobile indoor positioning system founded on convolutional extraction of learned WLAN fingerprints	2016	[14]
Conditional entropy and location error in indoor localization using probabilistic Wi-Fi fingerprinting	2016	[15]
Ensembles of indoor positioning systems based on fingerprinting: Simplifying parameter selection and obtaining robust systems	2016	[16]
Extremely randomized trees for Wi-Fi fingerprint-based indoor positioning	2016	[17]
Position error and entropy of probabilistic Wi-Fi fingerprinting in the UJIIndoorLoc dataset	2016	[18]
A deep learning approach to fingerprinting indoor localization solutions	2017	[19]
A Hierarchical Mixture Density Network	2017	[20]
A novel methodology to estimate a measurement of the inherent difficulty of an indoor localization radio map	2017	[21]
A realistic evaluation of indoor positioning systems based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting: The 2015 EvAAL-ETRI competition	2017	[22]
A smartphone-based indoor localisation system using FM and Wi-Fi signals	2017	[23]
Adopting the FAB-MAP algorithm for indoor localization with WiFi fingerprints	2017	[24]
Comparison of similarity approaches for indoor localization	2017	[25]
Detecting Rogue AP with the Crowd Wisdom	2017	[26]
Feature extraction and learning for RSSI based indoor device localization	2017	[27]
IndoorLoc platform: A public repository for comparing and evaluating indoor positioning systems	2017	[28]
Large-Scale Location-Aware Services in Access: Hierarchical Building/Floor Classification and Location Estimation Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Based on Deep Neural Networks	2017	[29]
Low-effort place recognition with WiFi fingerprints using deep learning	2017	[30]
Smart probabilistic approach with RSSI fingerprinting for indoor localization	2017	[31]
Using dimensionality reduction techniques for refining passive indoor positioning systems based on radio fingerprinting	2017	[32]

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TABLE II
LIST OF 283 WORKS PUBLISHED IN 2015–2024 CITING AND USING THE UJIINDOORLOC EMPIRICALLY [1], [2] (CONTINUATION)

Manuscript title	Year	Ref.
A scalable deep neural network architecture for multi-building and multi-floor indoor localization based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting	2018	[33]
A Soft Range Limited K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm for Indoor Localization Enhancement	2018	[34]
Adopting Learning-based Visual Localization Methods for Indoor Positioning with WiFi Fingerprints	2018	[35]
An advanced algorithm for Fingerprint Localization based on Kalman Filter	2018	[36]
Automatic building and floor classification using two consecutive multi-layer perceptron	2018	[37]
CDM: Compound Dissimilarity Measure and an Application to Fingerprinting-Based Positioning	2018	[38]
CNN based Indoor Localization using RSS Time-Series	2018	[39]
Dimension reduction in radio maps based on the supervised kernel principal component analysis	2018	[40]
Efficient and robust WiFi indoor positioning using hierarchical navigable small world graphs	2018	[41]
HybLoc: Hybrid indoor wi-fi localization using soft clustering-based random decision forest ensembles	2018	[42]
Indoor Localization with WiFi Fingerprinting Using Convolutional Neural Network	2018	[43]
Indoor Positioning Using WiFi Fingerprint	2018	[44]
Infinite-term memory classifier for wi-fi localization based on dynamic Wi-Fi Simulator	2018	[45]
Position Quantization Approach with Multi-class Classification for Wi-Fi Indoor Positioning System	2018	[46]
Probabilistic approach by using N-peak Gaussian distribution for indoor positioning	2018	[47]
Received Signal Strength Quantization for Secure Indoor Positioning via Fingerprinting	2018	[48]
Robust radio localization with FLIP	2018	[49]
Steering Crowdsourced Signal Map Construction via Bayesian Compressive Sensing	2018	[50]
Top-down indoor localization with Wi-Fi fingerprints using deep Q-network	2018	[51]
TrueStory: Accurate and Robust RF-Based Floor Estimation for Challenging Indoor Environments	2018	[52]
Unsupervised Deep Feature Learning to Reduce the Collection of Fingerprints for Indoor Localization Using Deep Belief Networks	2018	[53]
A hybrid model based on constraint OSELM, adaptive weighted SRC and KNN for large-scale indoor localization	2019	[54]
A Novel Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization Framework with WiFi Fingerprinting	2019	[55]
A Qualitative and Quantitative Evaluation of Differential Signal Strength Fingerprinting Methods	2019	[56]
A wifi positioning algorithm based on deep learning	2019	[57]
A wifi positioning method based on stack auto encoder	2019	[58]
Cascaded layered recurrent neural network for indoor localization in wireless sensor networks	2019	[59]
Cnnloc: Deep-learning based indoor localization with wifi fingerprinting	2019	[60]
Cross-device radio map generation via crowdsourcing	2019	[61]
Detecting high indoor crowd density with Wi-Fi localization: a statistical mechanics approach	2019	[62]
Feature selection on database optimization for Wi-Fi fingerprint indoor positioning	2019	[63]
Hierarchical fusion of machine learning algorithms in indoor positioning and localization	2019	[64]
Knowledge preserving OSELM model for Wi-Fi-based indoor localization	2019	[65]
Machine learning applied to wi-fi fingerprinting: The experiences of the ubiqum challenge	2019	[66]
Machine learning based indoor localization using wi-fi fingerprinting	2019	[67]
MFA-OSELM algorithm for WiFi-based indoor positioning system	2019	[68]
Performance Comparison of Indoor Fingerprinting Techniques Based on Artificial Neural Network	2019	[69]
Recurrent Neural Networks for Accurate RSSI Indoor Localization	2019	[70]
Scaled conjugate gradient neural network for optimizing indoor positioning system	2019	[71]
Selecting Critical WiFi APs for Indoor Localization Based on a Theoretical Error Analysis	2019	[72]
Semi-supervised variational autoencoder for WiFi indoor localization	2019	[73]
Stacked auto-encoder for scalable indoor localization in wireless sensor networks	2019	[74]
A Novel Weighted KNN Algorithm Based on RSS Similarity and Position Distance for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Positioning	2020	[75]
Adaptive Density Graph-Based Manifold Alignment for Fingerprinting Indoor Localization	2020	[76]
Analysis of received signal strength quantization in fingerprinting localization	2020	[77]
DL-RNN: An Accurate Indoor Localization Method via Double RNNs	2020	[78]
Faster Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Using Feature Selection	2020	[79]
Feature Engineering for Grid-based Multi-Floor Indoor Localisation using Machine Learning	2020	[80]
Federated Learning for RSS Fingerprint-based Localization: A Privacy-Preserving Crowdsourcing Method	2020	[81]
Let's forget about exact signal strength: Indoor positioning based on access point ranking and recurrent neural networks	2020	[82]
New Cluster Selection and Fine-grained Search for k-Means Clustering and Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2020	[83]
Privacy-Aware Sensing-Quality-Based Budget Feasible Incentive Mechanism for Crowdsourcing Fingerprint Collection	2020	[84]
Pseudo Label-Driven Federated Learning-Based Decentralized Indoor Localization via Mobile Crowdsourcing	2020	[85]
Residual Neural Networks for Heterogeneous Smart Device Localization in IoT Networks	2020	[86]
Robust and accurate Wi-Fi fingerprint location recognition method based on deep neural network	2020	[87]
Robust indoor localization methods using random forest-based filter against mac spoofing attack	2020	[88]
RSS Fingerprinting Dataset Size Reduction Using Feature-Wise Adaptive k-Means Clustering	2020	[89]
The storyteller: Scalable building- and ap-independent deep learning-based floor prediction	2020	[90]
TILoc: Improving the Robustness and Accuracy for Fingerprint-Based Indoor Localization	2020	[91]
Variational information bottleneck model for accurate indoor position recognition	2020	[92]
Verifiable Edge Computing for Indoor Positioning	2020	[93]
WiFi fingerprint positioning method based on fusion of autoencoder and stacking mode	2020	[94]
WiFi Fingerprinting based Floor Detection with Hierarchical Extreme Learning Machine	2020	[95]

TABLE III
LIST OF 283 WORKS PUBLISHED IN 2015–2024 CITING AND USING THE UJIINDOORLOC EMPIRICALLY [1], [2] (CONTINUATION)

Manuscript title	Year	Ref.
A Bisection Reinforcement Learning Approach to 3-D Indoor Localization	2021	[96]
A Novel GCN based Indoor Localization System with Multiple Access Points	2021	[97]
A Privacy-Preserved Online Personalized Federated Learning Framework for Indoor Localization	2021	[98]
A small world graph approach for an efficient indoor positioning system	2021	[99]
A universal Wi-Fi fingerprint localization method based on machine learning and sample differences	2021	[100]
Accurate Indoor Positioning Based on Learned Absolute and Relative Models	2021	[101]
Adversarial Attacks on Deep Learning-based Floor Classification and Indoor Localization	2021	[102]
An accurate WiFi indoor positioning algorithm for complex pedestrian environments	2021	[103]
Beyond Euclidean Distance for Error Measurement in Pedestrian Indoor Location	2021	[104]
C-CNNLoc: Constrained CNN for robust indoor localization with building boundary	2021	[105]
Cpos: Wifi fingerprint indoor positioning system based on cdae-cnn	2021	[106]
Data Cleaning for Indoor Crowdsourced RSSI Sequences	2021	[107]
Deeplocbox: Reliable fingerprinting-based indoor area localization	2021	[108]
Designing an ensemble of classifiers for smartphone-based indoor localization irrespective of device configuration	2021	[109]
Distance Metric Learning for Radio Fingerprinting Localization	2021	[110]
Enhanced fingerprinting based indoor positioning using machine learning	2021	[111]
GAN Based Data Augmentation for Indoor Localization Using Labeled and Unlabeled Data	2021	[112]
Hierarchical Multi-Building And Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based On Recurrent Neural Networks	2021	[113]
Hybrid Machine Learning Classifiers for Indoor User Localization Problem	2021	[114]
Indoor localization for personalized ambient assisted living of multiple users in multi-floor smart environments	2021	[115]
Indoor Localization Using Data Augmentation via Selective Generative Adversarial Networks	2021	[116]
Indoor Localization using Graph Neural Networks	2021	[117]
Jlgbmlc—a novel high-precision indoor localization method based on lightgbm	2021	[118]
Lightweight Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with a Novel RSS Clustering Algorithm	2021	[119]
Local-level Analysis of Positioning Errors in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2021	[120]
Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on RBF Network with Initialization, Calibration, and Update	2021	[121]
Neighbor Oblivious Learning (NOBLE) for Device Localization and Tracking	2021	[122]
Novel weighted ensemble classifier for smartphone based indoor localization	2021	[123]
Personalized Federated Learning over non-IID Data for Indoor Localization	2021	[124]
QuickLoc: Adaptive deep-learning for fast indoor localization with mobile devices	2021	[125]
RAD-GAN: Radio Map Anomaly Detection for Fingerprint Indoor Positioning with GAN	2021	[126]
SMOTE for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Construction in Indoor Positioning Systems	2021	[127]
Students Trajectory Pattern Finding Scheme Based on RSSI Geolocation as a Part of Smart Campus	2021	[128]
Supervised and semi-supervised deep probabilistic models for indoor positioning problems	2021	[129]
The analysis of feature selection with machine learning for indoor positioning	2021	[130]
Topology Preserving Input Image for Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization	2021	[131]
Traceall: A real-time processing for contact tracing using indoor trajectories	2021	[132]
Transfer Learning for Convolutional Indoor Positioning Systems	2021	[133]
WKNN indoor Wi-Fi localization method using k-means clustering based radio mapping	2021	[134]
A Deep Neural Network Based on Stacked Auto-encoder and Dataset Stratification in Indoor Location	2021	[135]
A Comprehensive and Reproducible Comparison of Clustering and Optimization Rules in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2022	[136]
A fingerprint-based localization algorithm based on LSTM and data expansion method for sparse samples	2022	[137]
A Framework for Indoor Positioning Including Building Topology	2022	[138]
A genetic programming approach to WiFi fingerprint meta-distance learning	2022	[139]
A hierarchical auxiliary deep neural network architecture for large-scale indoor localization based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting	2022	[140]
A novel feature based ensemble learning model for indoor localization of smartphone users	2022	[141]
A Novel Indoor Fingerprint Localization System Based on Distance Metric Learning and AP Selection	2022	[142]
A Novel Weighted Fusion based Efficient Clustering for Improved Wi-Fi Fingerprint Indoor Positioning	2022	[143]
Affinity propagation clustering-aided two-label hierarchical extreme learning machine for Wi-Fi fingerprinting-based indoor positioning	2022	[144]
An Indoor Floor Location Method Based on Minimum Received Signal Strength (RSS) Dynamic Compensation and Multi Label Classification	2022	[145]
Artificial intelligence techniques in wireless sensor networks for accurate localization of user in floor, building and indoor area	2022	[146]
Calibration-free 3D indoor positioning algorithms based on DNN and DIFF	2022	[147]
CHISEL: Compression-Aware High-Accuracy Embedded Indoor Localization With Deep Learning	2022	[148]
Clustering indoor location data for social distancing and human mobility to combat covid-19	2022	[149]
Communication-efficient Federated Indoor Localization with Layerwise Swapping Training-Fed Avg	2022	[150]
DNN-Based Indoor Localization Under Limited Dataset Using GANs and Semi-Supervised Learning	2022	[151]
EdgeLoc: A Robust and Real-Time Localization System Toward Heterogeneous IoT Devices	2022	[152]
Enhanced Radio Map Interpolation Methods Based on Dimensionality Reduction and Clustering	2022	[153]
Federated Learning for Indoor Localization via Model Reliability with Dropout	2022	[154]
Federated Learning-Based Localization With Heterogeneous Fingerprint Database	2022	[155]
Fi-Vi: Large-Area Indoor Localization Scheme Combining ML/DL-Based Wireless Fingerprinting and Visual Positioning	2022	[156]
Fingerprint Image-Based Multi-Building 3D Indoor Wi-Fi Localization Using Convolutional Neural Networks	2022	[157]
Floor Identification in Large-Scale Environments with Wi-Fi Autonomous Block Models	2022	[158]

TABLE IV
LIST OF 283 WORKS PUBLISHED IN 2015–2024 CITING AND USING THE UJIINDOORLOC EMPIRICALLY [1], [2] (CONTINUATION)

Manuscript title	Year	Ref.
Hierarchical fingerprinting and feature extraction for indoor localization	2022	[159]
Indoor Wi-Fi Fingerprint Localization Based on SDAE and MLP with Self-attention Mechanism	2022	[160]
Intelligent Positioning System: Learning Indoor Mobility Behavior and Batch Affiliations	2022	[161]
Lightweight Hybrid CNN-ELM Model for Multi-building and Multi-floor Classification	2022	[162]
MRILoc: Multiresolution Indoor Localization from crowdsourced samples	2022	[163]
Multi-floor Indoor Location Method Based on Fusion-CNN	2022	[164]
Multi-floor Positioning Method based on RSSI in Wireless Sensor Networks	2022	[165]
Multi-Output Gaussian Process-Based Data Augmentation for Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization	2022	[166]
Multi-Task Neural Network for Position Estimation in Large-Scale Indoor Environments	2022	[167]
On the privacy protection of indoor location dataset using anonymization	2022	[168]
ONavi: Data-driven based Multi-sensor Fusion Positioning System in Indoor Environments	2022	[169]
Optimum NN Algorithms Parameters on the UJIIndoorLoc for Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Indoor Positioning Systems	2022	[170]
Performance analysis of adaptive K for weighted K-nearest neighbor based indoor positioning	2022	[171]
Prediction Based Semi-Supervised Online Personalized Federated Learning for Indoor Localization	2022	[172]
Providing Location Information at Edge Networks: A Federated Learning-Based Approach	2022	[173]
Robust Bayesian Learning for Reliable Wireless AI: Framework and Applications	2022	[174]
SELE: RSS-Based Siamese Embedding Location Estimator for a Dynamic IoT Environment	2022	[175]
Towards Accelerated Localization Performance Across Indoor Positioning Datasets	2022	[176]
Towards Floor Identification and Pinpointing Position: A Multistory Localization Model with WiFi Fingerprint	2022	[177]
TWO-PHASE COMBINED MODEL TO IMPROVE THE ACCURACY OF INDOOR LOCATION FINGERPRINTING	2022	[178]
What You Sense is Not Where You are: On the Relationships between Fingerprints and Spatial Knowledge in Indoor Positioning	2022	[179]
Wi-Fi fingerprinting-based floor detection using adaptive scaling and weighted autoencoder extreme learning machine	2022	[180]
Wi-Fi indoor 3D localization algorithm based on multi-classifier fusion	2022	[181]
WiFi Based Distance Estimation Using Supervised Machine Learning	2022	[182]
WiFi Indoor Location Based on Area Segmentation	2022	[183]
XGBLoc: XGBoost-Based Indoor Localization in Multi-Building Multi-Floor Environments	2022	[184]
Zone-Based Federated Learning in Indoor Positioning	2022	[185]
A high available and strong generalization capability data-driven-based wireless fingerprint positioning model	2023	[186]
A Local Machine Learning Approach for Fingerprint-based Indoor Localization	2023	[187]
A Ranking-Based Feature Selection For Indoor Positioning System	2023	[188]
A Robust WiFi Localization Algorithm Using Data Augmentation and Stacked Denoising Autoencoder	2023	[189]
A tutorial on Federated Learning methodology for indoor localization with non-IID fingerprint databases	2023	[190]
A WiFi Fingerprint Indoor Location Framework Based on Convolutional Neural Network	2023	[191]
An Efficient and Robust Fingerprint Based Localization Method for Multi Floor Indoor Environment	2023	[192]
An improved WiFi sensing based indoor navigation with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for 6G enabled IoT network and AI explainable use case	2023	[193]
An Indoor Localization Mechanisms Based on Local Differential Privacy	2023	[194]
Demo Abstract: Real-Time 3D Indoor Localization with Multi-Dimensional RSSI on Mobile Robot	2023	[195]
DP-Loc: A Differential Privacy-Based Indoor Localization Scheme with Bilateral Privacy Protection	2023	[196]
EA-CNN: A smart indoor 3D positioning scheme based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting and deep learning	2023	[197]
EWok: Towards Efficient Multidimensional Compression of Indoor Positioning Datasets	2023	[198]
Exploiting Unlabeled RSSI Fingerprints in Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization through Deep Semi-Supervised Learning Based on Mean Teacher	2023	[199]
extendGAN+: Transferable Data Augmentation Framework Using WGAN-GP for Data-Driven Indoor Localisation Model	2023	[200]
GConvLoc: WiFi Fingerprinting-Based Indoor Localization Using Graph Convolutional Networks	2023	[201]
Graph-Based Radio Fingerprint Augmentation for Deep-Learning-Based Indoor Localization	2023	[202]
High-Performance Features in Generalizable Fingerprint-Based Indoor Positioning	2023	[203]
Indoor Dual-indicator Precision Localization Network based on Multitask Learning	2023	[204]
Indoor Keyless Entry Systems with Wi-Fi Fingerprint and Ensemble Learning Regression-Classification Model	2023	[205]
IndoorGNN: A Graph Neural Network Based Approach for Indoor Localization Using WiFi RSSI	2023	[206]
Let's Talk about k-NN for Indoor Positioning: Myths and Facts in RF-based Fingerprinting	2023	[207]
Localization of Multi-Building Floors Based on Wavelet-CNN	2023	[208]
Multi-Level Feature Extraction and Autoregressive Prediction Based Wi-Fi Indoor Fingerprint Localization	2023	[209]
Neural-Network-Based Localization Method for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Indoor Localization	2023	[210]
PSOSVRPos: WiFi indoor positioning using SVR optimized by PSO	2023	[211]
Scalable and Efficient Clustering for Fingerprint-Based Positioning	2023	[212]
Scalable Indoor Wi-Fi Positioning Algorithm Using Cluster-Based Local Estimators	2023	[213]
SE-Loc: Security-Enhanced Indoor Localization with Semi-Supervised Deep Learning	2023	[214]
Self-attention-based multimodality convolutional volcano eruption network based indoor localization and wayfinding for blind people	2023	[215]
Semi-supervised learning with network embedding on ambient rf signals for geofencing services	2023	[216]
Stage-Wise and Hierarchical Training of Linked Deep Neural Networks for Large-Scale Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2023	[217]
Supervised Learning-Based Indoor Positioning System Using WiFi Fingerprints	2023	[218]
Towards interpretability in fingerprint based indoor positioning: May attention be with us	2023	[219]
Towards Learning an Optimal Metric for Fingerprint-based Localisation	2023	[220]
Towards Quality Wi-Fi Synthetic Data for Indoor Positioning Evaluation	2023	[221]

TABLE V
LIST OF 283 WORKS PUBLISHED IN 2015–2024 CITING AND USING THE UJIINDOORLOC EMPIRICALLY [1], [2] (CONTINUATION)

Manuscript title	Year	Ref.
Using Filtered Synthetic Data and Cluster K-Nearest Neighbor to Enhance the Accuracy of Fingerprint-Based Indoor Localization	2023	[222]
Virtual Graph Neural Networks: A Novel Approach for Building-Agnostic Indoor Positioning System	2023	[223]
A Brownian Motion Restricted K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm for Indoor Positioning	2024	[224]
A deployable quantum access points selection algorithm for large-scale localization	2024	[225]
A Privacy-Preserving Indoor Localization System based on Hierarchical Federated Learning	2024	[226]
Accurate and efficient floor localization with scalable spiking graph neural networks	2024	[227]
Adversarial Contrastive Representation Learning for Passive WiFi Fingerprinting of Individuals	2024	[228]
Adversarial Examples Against WiFi Fingerprint-Based Localization in the Physical World	2024	[229]
Adversarial Machine Learning for Wireless Localization	2024	[230]
An Edge-based WiFi Fingerprinting Indoor Localization Using Convolutional Neural Network and Convolutional Auto-Encoder	2024	[231]
An Efficient and Robust Fingerprint-Based Localization Method for Multifloor Indoor Environment	2024	[232]
An efficient indoor localization for smartphone users: Hybrid metaheuristic optimization methodology	2024	[233]
An Efficient Quantum Binary-Neuron Algorithm for Accurate Multi-Story Floor Localization	2024	[234]
An explainable hybrid deep learning architecture for WiFi-based indoor localization in Internet of Things environment	2024	[235]
Analysis of the origin of differences in position among different fingerprinting datasets	2024	[236]
Asynchronous Federated Learning-Based Indoor Localization With Non-IID Data	2024	[237]
Augmenting Multidimensional Fingerprint with Wavelet Transform for Indoor Localization	2024	[238]
C2R: A Novel Architecture for Boosting Indoor Positioning With Scarce Data	2024	[239]
DeepFuzzLoc Positioning: A Unified Fusion of Fuzzy Clustering and Deep Learning for Scalable Indoor Localization Using Wi-Fi RSSI	2024	[240]
DeepRSSI: Generative Model for Fingerprint-Based Localization	2024	[241]
Detection of Access Point Spoofing in the Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Based Positioning	2024	[242]
Dimensionality Reduction Through Multiple Convolutional Channels for RSS-Based Indoor Localization	2024	[243]
DumbLoc: Dumb Indoor Localization Framework Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2024	[244]
Effect of Wi-Fi Access Points Spoofing on Fingerprinting Localization	2024	[245]
Enhancing the Explainability of Gradient Boosting Classification Through Comparable Samples Selection	2024	[246]
Enhancing Wi-Fi RSS-Based Indoor Positioning under Dynamic AP Availability: Leveraging Virtual Feature Maps and Contrastive Learning	2024	[247]
Exploiting 2-D Representations for Enhanced Indoor Localization: A Transfer Learning Approach	2024	[248]
Federated Fingerprint Localization Method Based on Adaptive Aggregation and Feature Alignment	2024	[249]
FEKNN: A Wi-Fi Indoor Localization Method Based on Feature Enhancement and KNN	2024	[250]
FeMLoc: Federated Meta-learning for Adaptive Wireless Indoor Localization Tasks in IoT Networks	2024	[251]
FGLNoRe: Federated Graph Learning on Non-IID RF Fingerprints for Building-Floor Positioning	2024	[252]
Gaussian Approximation-Based, Deep Neural Network-assisted Precise Indoor Localization	2024	[253]
Graph-Neural-Network-Based WiFi Indoor Localization System with Access Point Selection	2024	[254]
Hierarchical Stage-Wise Training of Linked Deep Neural Networks for Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on Wi-Fi RSSI Fingerprinting	2024	[255]
Hyperparameterless k-NN for Wi-Fi Fingerprinting	2024	[256]
HyTra: Hyperclass Transformer for WiFi Fingerprinting-based Indoor Localization	2024	[257]
Improved 3D Wireless Indoor Localization with Deep Learning Algorithms	2024	[258]
Improving Indoor WiFi Localization by Using Machine Learning Techniques	2024	[259]
Improving the sustainability of WiFi-enabled indoor localization systems through meta-heuristic based instance selection approach	2024	[260]
Indoor Localization of Resource-Constrained IoT Devices Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting and Convolutional Neural Network	2024	[261]
Indoor Localization via Deep Learning with Self-Attention and Stacked Denoising Autoencoders	2024	[262]
Indoor Localization With an Autoencoder-Based Convolutional Neural Network	2024	[263]
Indoor Localization with GravNetConv and Dynamic Graphs	2024	[264]
Indoor positioning fingerprint database construction based on CSA-DBSCAN and RCVAE-GAN	2024	[265]
Inverse distance weight-assisted particle swarm optimized indoor localization	2024	[266]
Learning-Based WiFi Fingerprint Inpainting via Generative Adversarial Networks	2024	[267]
Machine Learning Based Indoor Positioning System Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Dataset	2024	[268]
Machine Learning-Based WiFi Indoor Localization with FasterKAN: Optimizing Communication and Signal Accuracy	2024	[269]
Membership Inference Attacks Against Indoor Location Models	2024	[270]
Model Self-Supervised Federated Learning for Heterogeneous Fingerprint Localization	2024	[271]
Multi-Dimensional Wi-Fi Received Signal Strength Indicator Data Augmentation Based on Multi-Output Gaussian Process for Large-Scale Indoor Localization	2024	[272]
On the Use and Construction of Wi-Fi Fingerprint Databases for Large-Scale Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization: A Case Study of the UJIIndoorLoc Database	2024	[273]
On-device indoor positioning: A federated reinforcement learning approach with heterogeneous devices	2024	[274]
Privacy-Preserving WiFi Localization Based on Inner Product Encryption in a Cloud Environment	2024	[275]
SALoc: An Accurate Target Localization In Wifi-Enabled Indoor Environments Via Sae-Alstm	2024	[276]
Seeing the world from its words: All-embracing Transformers for fingerprint-based indoor localization	2024	[277]
Semi-Supervised Learning via Cross-Prediction-Powered Inference for Wireless Systems	2024	[278]
Three-Dimensional Wireless Indoor Localization with Machine Learning Algorithms for Location-Based IoT Applications	2024	[279]
tLoc: A Mathematical Probabilistic Model for Wireless Fingerprinting	2024	[280]
TransGAN-Based Secure Indoor Localization Against Adversarial Attacks	2024	[281]
WiFi Fingerprint Correction for Indoor Localization Based on Distance Metric Learning	2024	[282]
WIO-EKF: Extended Kalman Filtering-Based Wi-Fi and Inertial Odometry Fusion Method for Indoor Localization	2024	[283]
WKNN-Based Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with Deep Distance Metric Learning via Siamese Triplet Network for Indoor Positioning	2024	[284]
COVID-19 Contact Tracing Query Processing in IoT Using Spark	N/A	[285]
Tackling Fingerprinting Indoor Localization Using the LASSO and the Conjugate Gradient Algorithms	N/A	[286]

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Torres-Sospedra, R. Montoliu, A. Martínez-Usó, J. P. Avariento, T. J. Arnau, M. Benedito-Bordonau, and J. Huerta, "UJIIndoor-Loc: A new multi-building and multi-floor database for WLAN fingerprint-based indoor localization problems," en, in *2014 Int. Conf. on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, 2014, pp. 261–270.
- [2] J. Torres-Sospedra, R. Montoliu, A. Martínez-Usó, T. J. Arnau, and J. P. Avariento, "UJIIndoorLoc," UCI Repository of Machine Learning. DOI: 10.24432/C5MS59 [Online]. Available: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/310> (visited on 2025/08/11), 2014.
- [3] J. Torres-Sospedra, R. Montoliu, and A. Pérez-Navarro, "UJIIndoor-Loc Dataset: A Retrospective Analysis after 10 Years of Usage," in *Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, 2025.
- [4] S. Bozkurt, G. Elibol, S. Gunal, and U. Yayan, "A comparative study on machine learning algorithms for indoor positioning," in *INISTA 2015 - 2015 International Symposium on Innovations in Intelligent Systems and Applications, Proceedings*, 2015.
- [5] J. Torres-Sospedra, R. Montoliu, S. Trilles, Ó. Belmonte, and J. Huerta, "Comprehensive analysis of distance and similarity measures for Wi-Fi fingerprinting indoor positioning systems," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 42, no. 23, pp. 9263–9278, 2015.
- [6] J. Torres-Sospedra, J. Avariento, D. Rambla, R. Montoliu, S. Castleyn, M. Benedito-Bordonau, M. Gould, and J. Huerta, "Enhancing integrated indoor/outdoor mobility in a smart campus," *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, vol. 29, no. 11, pp. 1955–1968, 2015.
- [7] F. Potorti, P. Barsocchi, M. Girolami, J. Torres-Sospedra, and R. Montoliu, "Evaluating indoor localization solutions in large environments through competitive benchmarking: The EvAAL-ETRI competition," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2015*, 2015.
- [8] S. Knauth, M. Storz, H. Dastageeri, A. Koukofikis, and N. Mahser-Hipp, "Fingerprint calibrated centroid and scalar product correlation RSSI positioning in large environments," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2015*, 2015.
- [9] R. Berkvens, M. Weyn, and H. Peremans, "Localization performance quantification by conditional entropy," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2015*, 2015.
- [10] R. Berkvens, M. Weyn, and H. Peremans, "Mean mutual information of probabilistic wi-fi localization," in *Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN), 2015 International Conference*, 2015.
- [11] S. Jung, S.-I. Lee, S.-Y. Chi, and H. Choi, "POI estimation method with incremental update based on smartphones," in *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, vol. 20-23-October-2015, 2015, pp. 104–110.
- [12] A. Moreira, M. Nicolau, F. Meneses, and A. Costa, "Wi-Fi fingerprinting in the real world - RTLS@UM at the EvAAL competition," in *2015 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2015*, 2015.
- [13] J. Yin, Y. Wu, X. Zhang, and M. Lu, "A calibration-free crowdsourcing-based indoor localization solution," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10065 LNCS, 2016, pp. 65–76.
- [14] A. Bleiweiss, "A mobile indoor positioning system founded on convolutional extraction of learned WLAN fingerprints," in *ICPRAM 2016 - Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Pattern Recognition Applications and Methods*, 2016, pp. 214–223.
- [15] R. Berkvens, H. Peremans, and M. Weyn, "Conditional entropy and location error in indoor localization using probabilistic Wi-Fi fingerprinting," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 10, 2016.
- [16] J. Torres-Sospedra, G. Mendoza-Silva, R. Montoliu, O. Belmonte, F. Benitez, and J. Huerta, "Ensembles of indoor positioning systems based on fingerprinting: Simplifying parameter selection and obtaining robust systems," in *2016 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2016*, 2016.
- [17] M. Uddin and M. Islam, "Extremely randomized trees for Wi-Fi fingerprint-based indoor positioning," in *2015 18th International Conference on Computer and Information Technology, ICCIT 2015*, 2016, pp. 105–110.
- [18] R. Berkvens, M. Weyn, and H. Peremans, "Position error and entropy of probabilistic Wi-Fi fingerprinting in the UJIIndoorLoc dataset," in *2016 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2016*, 2016.
- [19] L. Xiao, A. Behboodi, and R. Mathar, "A deep learning approach to fingerprinting indoor localization solutions," in *2017 27th International Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference, ITNAC 2017*, vol. 2017-January, 2017, pp. 1–7.
- [20] F. Yang, J. Soriano, T. Kubo, and K. Ikeda, "A Hierarchical Mixture Density Network," in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10637 LNCS, 2017, pp. 878–885.
- [21] E. Sansano, R. Montoliu, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "A novel methodology to estimate a measurement of the inherent difficulty of an indoor localization radio map," in *2017 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2017*, vol. 2017-January, 2017, pp. 1–8.
- [22] J. Torres-Sospedra, A. Moreira, S. Knauth, R. Berkvens, R. Montoliu, O. Belmonte, S. Trilles, M. João Nicolau, F. Meneses, A. Costa, A. Koukofikis, M. Weyn, and H. Peremans, "A realistic evaluation of indoor positioning systems based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting: The 2015 EvAAL-ETRI competition," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart Environments*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 263–279, 2017.
- [23] A. Mukhopadhyay, P. Rajput, and S. Srirangarajan, "A smartphone-based indoor localisation system using FM and Wi-Fi signals," in *25th European Signal Processing Conference, EUSIPCO 2017*, 2017, pp. 2473–2477.
- [24] J. Wietrzykowski, M. Nowicki, and P. Skrzypczyński, "Adopting the FAB-MAP algorithm for indoor localization with WiFi fingerprints," in *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 550, 2017, pp. 585–594.
- [25] W. Njima, I. Ahriz, R. Zayani, M. Terre, and R. Bouallegue, "Comparison of similarity approaches for indoor localization," in *International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Computing, Networking and Communications*, vol. 2017-October, 2017, pp. 349–354.
- [26] T. Zhou, Z. Cai, B. Xiao, Y. Chen, and M. Xu, "Detecting Rogue AP with the Crowd Wisdom," in *Proceedings - International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems*, 2017, pp. 2327–2332.
- [27] S. Timotheatos, G. Tsagkatakis, P. Tsakalides, and P. Trahanias, "Feature extraction and learning for RSSI based indoor device localization," in *ESANN 2017 - Proceedings, 25th European Symposium on Artificial Neural Networks, Computational Intelligence and Machine Learning*, 2017, pp. 619–624.
- [28] R. Montoliu, E. Sansano, J. Torres-Sospedra, and O. Belmonte, "IndoorLoc platform: A public repository for comparing and evaluating indoor positioning systems," in *2017 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2017*, vol. 2017-January, 2017, pp. 1–8.
- [29] K. Kim, R. Wang, Z. Zhong, Z. Tan, H. Song, J. Cha, and S. Lee, "Large-scale location-aware services in access: Hierarchical building/floor classification and location estimation using Wi-Fi fingerprinting based on deep neural networks," in *2017 International Workshop on Fiber Optics in Access Network, FOAN 2017*, vol. 2017-December, 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [30] M. Nowicki and J. Wietrzykowski, "Low-effort place recognition with WiFi fingerprints using deep learning," in *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 550, 2017, pp. 575–584.
- [31] W. Njima, I. Ahriz, R. Zayani, M. Terre, and R. Bouallegue, "Smart probabilistic approach with RSSI fingerprinting for indoor localization," in *2017 25th International Conference on Software, Telecommunications and Computer Networks, SoftCOM 2017*, 2017.
- [32] P. Lopez-de-Teruel, O. Canovas, and F. Garcia, "Using dimensionality reduction techniques for refining passive indoor positioning systems based on radio fingerprinting," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 17, no. 4, 2017.
- [33] K. S. Kim, S. Lee, and K. Huang, "A scalable deep neural network architecture for multi-building and multi-floor indoor localization based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting," *Big Data Analytics*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 1–17, 2018.
- [34] M. Hoang, Y. Zhu, B. Yuen, T. Reese, X. Dong, T. Lu, R. Westendorp, and M. Xie, "A Soft Range Limited K-Nearest Neighbors

- Algorithm for Indoor Localization Enhancement,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 18, no. 24, pp. 10208–10216, 2018.
- [35] M. Nowicki, J. Wietrzykowski, and P. Skrzypczyński, “Adopting Learning-based Visual Localization Methods for Indoor Positioning with WiFi Fingerprints,” *Learning Applications for Intelligent Autonomous Robots*, 2018.
- [36] X. Wang and S. Cong, “An advanced algorithm for Fingerprint Localization based on Kalman Filter,” in *Proceedings of 5th IEEE Conference on Ubiquitous Positioning, Indoor Navigation and Location-Based Services, UPINLBS 2018*, 2018.
- [37] J. Cha, S. Lee, and K. Kim, “Automatic building and floor classification using two consecutive multi-layer perceptron,” in *International Conference on Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 2018-October, 2018, pp. 87–91.
- [38] C. Zhou and A. Wieser, “CDM: Compound Dissimilarity Measure and an Application to Fingerprinting-Based Positioning,” in *IPIN 2018 - 9th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation*, 2018.
- [39] M. Ibrahim, M. Torki, and M. Elnainay, “CNN based Indoor Localization using RSS Time-Series,” in *Proceedings - IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communications*, vol. 2018-June, 2018, pp. 1044–1049.
- [40] B. Jia, B. Huang, H. Gao, and W. Li, “Dimension reduction in radio maps based on the supervised kernel principal component analysis,” *Soft Computing*, vol. 22, no. 23, pp. 7697–7703, 2018.
- [41] M. Soares Lima, H. Fernandes De Oliveira, E. Dos Santos, E. De Moura, R. Costa, and M. Levorato, “Efficient and robust WiFi indoor positioning using hierarchical navigable small world graphs,” in *NCA 2018 - 2018 IEEE 17th International Symposium on Network Computing and Applications*, 2018.
- [42] B. Akram, A. Akbar, and O. Shafiq, “HybLoc: Hybrid indoor wi-fi localization using soft clustering-based random decision forest ensembles,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 38 251–38 272, 2018.
- [43] J.-W. Jang and S.-N. Hong, “Indoor Localization with WiFi Fingerprinting Using Convolutional Neural Network,” in *International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks, ICUFN*, vol. 2018-July, 2018, pp. 753–758.
- [44] R. Joseph and S. Sasi, “Indoor Positioning Using WiFi Fingerprint,” in *2018 International Conference on Circuits and Systems in Digital Enterprise Technology, ICCSDET 2018*, 2018.
- [45] A. Al-Khaleefa, M. Ahmad, A. Md Isa, M. Mohd Esa, A. Al-Saffar, and Y. Aljeroudi, “Infinite-term memory classifier for wi-fi localization based on dynamic Wi-Fi Simulator,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 54 769–54 785, 2018.
- [46] W. Charoenruangkit, S. Saejun, R. Jongfungfeuang, and K. Multhonggad, “Position Quantization Approach with Multi-class Classification for Wi-Fi Indoor Positioning System,” in *Proceeding of 2018 3rd International Conference on Information Technology, InCIT 2018*, 2018.
- [47] K. Mishev, A. Gjorgjevikj, and D. Trajanov, “Probabilistic approach by using N-peak Gaussian distribution for indoor positioning,” *ICT Innovations*, pp. 61–74, 2018.
- [48] P. Richter, Z. Yang, O. Tkachenko, H. Leppäkoski, K. Järvinen, T. Schneider, and E. Lohan, “Received Signal Strength Quantization for Secure Indoor Positioning via Fingerprinting,” in *ICL-GNSS 2018 - 2018 8th International Conference on Localization and GNSS: Seamless Indoor-Outdoor Localization, Proceedings*, 2018.
- [49] R. Müllner and T. Burgess, “Robust radio localization with FLIP,” in *2018 European Navigation Conference, ENC 2018*, 2018, pp. 19–26.
- [50] S. He and K. Shin, “Steering Crowdsourced Signal Map Construction via Bayesian Compressive Sensing,” in *Proceedings - IEEE INFOCOM*, vol. 2018-April, 2018, pp. 1016–1024.
- [51] F. Dou, J. Lu, Z. Wang, X. Xiao, J. Bi, and C.-H. Huang, “Top-down indoor localization with Wi-Fi fingerprints using deep Q-network,” in *Proceedings - 15th IEEE International Conference on Mobile Ad Hoc and Sensor Systems, MASS 2018*, 2018, pp. 166–174.
- [52] R. Elbakly, H. Aly, and M. Youssef, “TrueStory: Accurate and Robust RF-Based Floor Estimation for Challenging Indoor Environments,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 18, no. 24, pp. 10 115–10 124, 2018.
- [53] D. Le, N. Meratnia, and P. Havinga, “Unsupervised Deep Feature Learning to Reduce the Collection of Fingerprints for Indoor Localization Using Deep Belief Networks,” in *IPIN 2018 - 9th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation*, 2018.
- [54] H. Gan, M. Khir, G. Witjaksono Bin Djaswadi, and N. Ramli, “A hybrid model based on constraint OSELM, adaptive weighted SRC and KNN for large-scale indoor localization,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 6971–6989, 2019.
- [55] X. Song, X. Fan, C. Xiang, Q. Ye, L. Liu, Z. Wang, X. He, N. Yang, and G. Fang, “A Novel Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization Framework with WiFi Fingerprinting,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 110 698–110 709, 2019.
- [56] C. Laoudias, S. Kim, D. Zeinalipour-Yazti, and C. Panayiotou, “A Qualitative and Quantitative Evaluation of Differential Signal Strength Fingerprinting Methods,” in *IEEE International Conference on Communications*, vol. 2019-May, 2019.
- [57] Y. Zhong, Z. Yuan, Y. Li, and B. Yang, “A wifi positioning algorithm based on deep learning,” in *2019 7th International Conference on Information, Communication and Networks, ICIN 2019*, 2019, pp. 99–104.
- [58] Y. Zhong, Z. Yuan, S. Zhao, and X. Luo, “A wifi positioning method based on stack auto encoder,” in *Proceedings - 7th International Conference on Digital Home, ICDH 2018*, 2019, pp. 286–293.
- [59] H. Turabieh and A. Sheta, “Cascaded layered recurrent neural network for indoor localization in wireless sensor networks,” in *2019 2nd International Conference on New Trends in Computing Sciences, ICTCS 2019 - Proceedings*, 2019.
- [60] X. Song, X. Fan, X. He, C. Xiang, Q. Ye, X. Huang, G. Fang, L. Chen, J. Qin, and Z. Wang, “Cnnloc: Deep-learning based indoor localization with wifi fingerprinting,” in *Proceedings - 2019 IEEE SmartWorld, Ubiquitous Intelligence and Computing, Advanced and Trusted Computing, Scalable Computing and Communications, Internet of People and Smart City Innovation, SmartWorld/UIC/ATC/SCALCOM/IOP/SCI 2019*, 2019, pp. 589–595.
- [61] G. Pipelidis, N. Tsiमितros, E. Ustaoglu, R. Kienzler, P. Nurmi, H. Flores, and C. Prehofer, “Cross-device radio map generation via crowdsourcing,” in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2019*, 2019.
- [62] S. Georgievska, P. Rutten, J. Amoraal, E. Ranguelova, R. Bakhshi, B. de Vries, M. Lees, and S. Klous, “Detecting high indoor crowd density with Wi-Fi localization: A statistical mechanics approach,” *Journal of Big Data*, vol. 6, no. 1, 2019.
- [63] G. Apostolo, I. Sampaio, and J. Viterbo, “Feature selection on database optimization for Wi-Fi fingerprint indoor positioning,” in *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 159, 2019, pp. 251–260.
- [64] A. Seçkin and A. Coşkun, “Hierarchical fusion of machine learning algorithms in indoor positioning and localization,” *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 9, no. 18, 2019.
- [65] A. Al-Khaleefa, M. Ahmad, A. Isa, M. Esa, Y. Aljeroudi, M. Jubair, and R. Malik, “Knowledge preserving OSELM model for Wi-Fi-based indoor localization,” *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 19, no. 10, 2019.
- [66] J. Rojo, C. Corvalan, F. Unger, S. Lopez, I. Soteras, D. Bravo, J. Torres-Sospedra, G. Mendoza-Silva, G. Ristow Cidral, J. Laipea, G. Parrello, A. Simo, L. Stupin, D. Minican, and M. Farres, “Machine learning applied to wi-fi fingerprinting: The experiences of the ubiqum challenge,” in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2019*, 2019.
- [67] S. Wadhwa, P. Rai, and R. Kaushik, “Machine learning based indoor localization using wi-fi fingerprinting,” *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 502–506, 2019.
- [68] A. Al-Khaleefa, M. Ahmad, A. Isa, A. Al-Saffar, M. Esa, and R. Malik, “MFA-OSELM algorithm for WiFi-based indoor positioning system,” *Information (Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 4, 2019.
- [69] B. Soro and C. Lee, “Performance Comparison of Indoor Fingerprinting Techniques Based on Artificial Neural Network,” in *IEEE Region 10 Annual International Conference, Proceedings/TENCON*, vol. 2018-October, 2019, pp. 56–61.
- [70] M. Hoang, B. Yuen, X. Dong, T. Lu, R. Westendorp, and K. Reddy, “Recurrent Neural Networks for Accurate RSSI Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 10639–10651, 2019.
- [71] N. Aburaed, S. Atalla, H. Mukhtar, M. Al-Saad, and W. Mansoor, “Scaled conjugate gradient neural network for optimizing indoor

- positioning system,” in *2019 International Symposium on Networks, Computers and Communications, ISNCC 2019*, 2019.
- [72] B. Jia, B. Huang, H. Gao, W. Li, and L. Hao, “Selecting Critical WiFi APs for Indoor Localization Based on a Theoretical Error Analysis,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 36 312–36 321, 2019.
- [73] B. Chidlovskii and L. Antsfeld, “Semi-supervised variational auto-encoder for WiFi indoor localization,” in *2019 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2019*, 2019.
- [74] S. Belmannoubi, H. Touati, and H. Snoussi, “Stacked auto-encoder for scalable indoor localization in wireless sensor networks,” in *2019 15th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference, IWCMC 2019*, 2019, pp. 1245–1250.
- [75] B. Wang, X. Gan, X. Liu, B. Yu, R. Jia, L. Huang, and H. Jia, “A Novel Weighted KNN Algorithm Based on RSS Similarity and Position Distance for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Positioning,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 30 591–30 602, 2020.
- [76] S. Li, Q. Zhao, H. Li, S. Wang, T. Huang, and J. Liu, “Adaptive Density Graph-Based Manifold Alignment for Fingerprinting Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 4944–4953, 2020.
- [77] S. Khandker, J. Torres-Sospedra, and T. Ristaniemi, “Analysis of received signal strength quantization in fingerprinting localization,” *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 11, 2020.
- [78] S. Bai, M. Yan, Q. Wan, L. He, X. Wang, and J. Li, “DL-RNN: An Accurate Indoor Localization Method via Double RNNs,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 286–295, 2020.
- [79] H. Aydin, M. Ali, and E. Soyak, “Faster Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Using Feature Selection,” in *2020 28th Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference, SIU 2020 - Proceedings*, 2020.
- [80] S. Yean, B.-S. Lee, and H. Oh, “Feature Engineering for Grid-based Multi-Floor Indoor Localisation using Machine Learning,” in *2020 International Conference on Intelligent Data Science Technologies and Applications, IDSTA 2020*, 2020, pp. 142–148.
- [81] B. Ciftler, A. Albaseer, N. Lasla, and M. Abdallah, “Federated Learning for RSS Fingerprint-based Localization: A Privacy-Preserving Crowdsourcing Method,” in *2020 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing, IWCMC 2020*, 2020, pp. 2112–2117.
- [82] N. Saccomanno, A. Brunello, and A. Montanari, “Let’s forget about exact signal strength: Indoor positioning based on access point ranking and recurrent neural networks,” in *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 2020, pp. 215–224.
- [83] J. Torres-Sospedra, D. Quezada-Gaibor, G. Mendoza-Silva, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, and J. Huerta, “New Cluster Selection and Fine-grained Search for k-Means Clustering and Wi-Fi Fingerprinting,” in *2020 International Conference on Localization and GNSS, ICL-GNSS 2020 - Proceedings*, 2020.
- [84] W. Li, C. Zhang, and Y. Tanaka, “Privacy-Aware Sensing-Quality-Based Budget Feasible Incentive Mechanism for Crowdsourcing Fingerprint Collection,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 49 775–49 784, 2020.
- [85] W. Li, C. Zhang, and Y. Tanaka, “Pseudo Label-Driven Federated Learning-Based Decentralized Indoor Localization via Mobile Crowdsourcing,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 20, no. 19, pp. 11 556–11 565, 2020.
- [86] P. Pandey, P. Tiwary, S. Kumar, and S. Das, “Residual Neural Networks for Heterogeneous Smart Device Localization in IoT Networks,” in *Proceedings - International Conference on Computer Communications and Networks, ICCCN*, vol. 2020-August, 2020.
- [87] Y. Wang, J. Gao, Z. Li, and L. Zhao, “Robust and accurate Wi-Fi fingerprint location recognition method based on deep neural network,” *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2020.
- [88] D. Ko, S.-H. Choi, S. Ahn, and Y.-H. Choi, “Robust indoor localization methods using random forest-based filter against mac spoofing attack,” *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 20, no. 23, pp. 1–13, 2020.
- [89] L. Klus, D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, E. Lohan, C. Granell, and J. Nurmi, “RSS Fingerprinting Dataset Size Reduction Using Feature-Wise Adaptive k-Means Clustering,” in *International Congress on Ultra Modern Telecommunications and Control Systems and Workshops*, vol. 2020-October, 2020, pp. 195–200.
- [90] R. Elbakly and M. Youssef, “The storyteller: Scalable building- and ap-independent deep learning-based floor prediction,” *Proceedings of the ACM on Interactive, Mobile, Wearable and Ubiquitous Technologies*, vol. 4, no. 1, 2020.
- [91] H. Li, Z. Qian, C. Tian, and X. Wang, “TILoc: Improving the Robustness and Accuracy for Fingerprint-Based Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 3053–3066, 2020.
- [92] W. Qian and F. Gechter, “Variational information bottleneck model for accurate indoor position recognition,” in *Proceedings - International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, 2020, pp. 2529–2535.
- [93] S. Liu and Z. Yan, “Verifiable Edge Computing for Indoor Positioning,” in *IEEE International Conference on Communications*, vol. 2020-June, 2020.
- [94] G. JunLin, Z. Xin, W. HuaDeng, and Y. Lan, “WiFi fingerprint positioning method based on fusion of autoencoder and stacking mode,” in *2020 International Conference on Culture-Oriented Science & Technology (ICCST)*, IEEE, 2020, pp. 356–361.
- [95] A. Alitaloshi, H. Jazayeriy, and S. Kazemitabar, “WiFi Fingerprinting based Floor Detection with Hierarchical Extreme Learning Machine,” in *2020 10th International Conference on Computer and Knowledge Engineering, ICCKE 2020*, 2020, pp. 113–117.
- [96] F. Dou, J. Lu, T. Xu, C.-H. Huang, and J. Bi, “A Bisection Reinforcement Learning Approach to 3-D Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 8, no. 8, pp. 6519–6535, 2021.
- [97] Y. Sun, Q. Xie, G. Pan, S. Zhang, and S. Xu, “A Novel GCN based Indoor Localization System with Multiple Access Points,” in *2021 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing, IWCMC 2021*, 2021, pp. 9–14.
- [98] Z. Wu, X. Wu, X. Long, and Y. Long, “A Privacy-Preserved Online Personalized Federated Learning Framework for Indoor Localization,” in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, IEEE, 2021, pp. 2834–2839.
- [99] M. Lima, L. Guimarães, E. Santos, E. Moura, R. Costa, M. Levorato, and H. Oliveira, “A small world graph approach for an efficient indoor positioning system,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 15, 2021.
- [100] X. Cao, Y. Zhuang, X. Yang, X. Sun, and X. Wang, “A universal Wi-Fi fingerprint localization method based on machine learning and sample differences,” *Satellite Navigation*, vol. 2, no. 1, 2021.
- [101] C. Kjellson, M. Larsson, K. Astrom, and M. Oskarsson, “Accurate Indoor Positioning Based on Learned Absolute and Relative Models,” in *2021 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021*, 2021.
- [102] M. Patil, X. Wang, X. Wang, and S. Mao, “Adversarial Attacks on Deep Learning-based Floor Classification and Indoor Localization,” in *WiseML 2021 - Proceedings of the 3rd ACM Workshop on Wireless Security and Machine Learning*, 2021, pp. 7–12.
- [103] D. Yu and C. Li, “An accurate WiFi indoor positioning algorithm for complex pedestrian environments,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 21, no. 21, pp. 24 440–24 452, 2021.
- [104] G. Mendoza-Silva, J. Torres-Sospedra, F. Potorti, A. Moreira, S. Knauth, R. Berkvens, and J. Huerta, “Beyond Euclidean Distance for Error Measurement in Pedestrian Indoor Location,” *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 70, 2021.
- [105] Y. Oh, H.-M. Noh, and W. Shin, “C-CNNLoc: Constrained CNN for robust indoor localization with building boundary,” *Electronics Letters*, vol. 57, no. 10, pp. 422–425, 2021.
- [106] F. Qin, T. Zuo, and X. Wang, “Ccpos: Wifi fingerprint indoor positioning system based on cdae-cnn,” *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1–17, 2021.
- [107] J. Sun, B. Wang, X. Song, and X. Yang, “Data Cleaning for Indoor Crowdsourced RSSI Sequences,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 12859 LNCS, 2021, pp. 267–275.
- [108] M. Laska and J. Blankenbach, “Deeplocbox: Reliable fingerprinting-based indoor area localization,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 1–23, 2021.
- [109] P. Roy and C. Chowdhury, “Designing an ensemble of classifiers for smartphone-based indoor localization irrespective of device configuration,” *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 80, no. 13, pp. 20 501–20 525, 2021.
- [110] S. Bai, Y. Luo, M. Yan, and Q. Wan, “Distance Metric Learning for Radio Fingerprinting Localization,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 163, 2021.
- [111] M. Pasha, M. Umair, A. Mirza, F. Rao, A. Wakeel, S. Akram, F. Subhan, and W. Khan, “Enhanced fingerprinting based indoor positioning using machine learning,” *Computers, Materials and Continua*, vol. 69, no. 2, pp. 1631–1652, 2021.

- [112] W. Njima, M. Chafii, and R. Shubair, "GAN Based Data Augmentation for Indoor Localization Using Labeled and Unlabeled Data," in *2021 International Balkan Conference on Communications and Networking, BalkanCom 2021*, 2021, pp. 36–39.
- [113] A. Ahmed Elesawi and K. Kim, "Hierarchical Multi-Building And Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based On Recurrent Neural Networks," in *Proceedings - 2021 9th International Symposium on Computing and Networking Workshops, CANDARW 2021*, 2021, pp. 193–196.
- [114] H. Turabieh and A. S. Alghamdi, "Hybrid Machine Learning Classifiers for Indoor User Localization Problem," *International Journal*, no. 3, pp. 49–53, 2021.
- [115] N. Thakur and C. Han, "Indoor localization for personalized ambient assisted living of multiple users in multi-floor smart environments," *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 5, no. 3, 2021.
- [116] W. Njima, M. Chafii, A. Chorti, R. Shubair, and H. Poor, "Indoor Localization Using Data Augmentation via Selective Generative Adversarial Networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 98 337–98 347, 2021.
- [117] F. Lezama, G. Gonzalez, F. Larroca, and G. Capdehourat, "Indoor Localization using Graph Neural Networks," in *2021 IEEE URUCON, URUCON 2021*, 2021, pp. 51–54.
- [118] L. Yin, P. Ma, and Z. Deng, "Jlgbmloc—a novel high-precision indoor localization method based on lightgbm," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 8, 2021.
- [119] D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, and J. Huerta, "Lightweight Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with a Novel RSS Clustering Algorithm," in *2021 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021*, 2021.
- [120] G. Mendoza-Silva, J. Torres-Sospedra, and J. Huerta, "Local-level Analysis of Positioning Errors in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting," in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*, vol. 2021-April, 2021.
- [121] L. Yang, Y. Yu, and B. Li, "Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on RBF Network with Initialization, Calibration, and Update," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 20, no. 12, pp. 7977–7991, 2021.
- [122] Z. Liu, L. Chou, and A. Shrivastava, "Neighbor Oblivious Learning (NOBLE) for Device Localization and Tracking," in *Proceedings - Design, Automation and Test in Europe, DATE*, vol. 2021-February, 2021, pp. 1426–1429.
- [123] P. Roy, C. Chowdhury, M. Kundu, D. Ghosh, and S. Bandyopadhyay, "Novel weighted ensemble classifier for smartphone based indoor localization," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 164, 2021.
- [124] P. Wu, T. Imbiriba, J. Park, S. Kim, and P. Closas, "Personalized Federated Learning over non-IID Data for Indoor Localization," in *IEEE Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications, SPAWC*, vol. 2021-September, 2021, pp. 421–425.
- [125] S. Tiku, P. Kale, and S. Pasricha, "QuickLoc: Adaptive deep-learning for fast indoor localization with mobile devices," *ACM Transactions on Cyber-Physical Systems*, vol. 5, no. 4, 2021.
- [126] H. Ai, T. Hu, and T. Xu, "RAD-GAN: Radio Map Anomaly Detection for Fingerprint Indoor Positioning with GAN," in *2021 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021*, 2021.
- [127] Y. Yong, C. Tan, and I. Tan, "SMOTE for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Construction in Indoor Positioning Systems," in *Conference Proceedings of the IEEE International Performance, Computing, and Communications Conference*, vol. 2021-October, 2021.
- [128] R. Hastari, M. Yuliana, and P. Kristalina, "Students Trajectory Pattern Finding Scheme Based on RSSI Geolocation as a Part of Smart Campus," in *International Electronics Symposium 2021: Wireless Technologies and Intelligent Systems for Better Human Lives, IES 2021 - Proceedings*, 2021, pp. 337–342.
- [129] W. Qian, F. Lauri, and F. Gechter, "Supervised and semi-supervised deep probabilistic models for indoor positioning problems," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 435, pp. 228–238, 2021.
- [130] H. Aydin, M. Ali, and E. Soyak, "The analysis of feature selection with machine learning for indoor positioning," in *SIU 2021 - 29th IEEE Conference on Signal Processing and Communications Applications, Proceedings*, 2021.
- [131] M. Laska and J. Blankenbach, "Topology Preserving Input Image for Convolutional Neural Network Based Indoor Localization," in *2021 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021*, 2021.
- [132] L. Alarabi, S. Basalamah, A. Hendawi, and M. Abdalla, "Traceall: A real-time processing for contact tracing using indoor trajectories," *Information (Switzerland)*, vol. 12, no. 5, 2021.
- [133] R. Klus, L. Klus, J. Talvitie, J. Pihlajasalo, J. Torres-Sospedra, and M. Valkama, "Transfer Learning for Convolutional Indoor Positioning Systems," in *2021 International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation, IPIN 2021*, 2021.
- [134] S. Liu, R. De Lacerda, and J. Fiorina, "WKNN indoor Wi-Fi localization method using k-means clustering based radio mapping," in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference*, vol. 2021-April, 2021.
- [135] J. Zhang and Y. Su, "A Deep Neural Network Based on Stacked Auto-encoder and Dataset Stratification in Indoor Location," en, in *Computational Science – ICCS 2021*, M. Paszynski, D. Kranzlmüller, V. V. Krzhizhanovskaya, J. J. Dongarra, and P. M. A. Sloot, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 33–46.
- [136] J. Torres-Sospedra, P. Richter, A. Moreira, G. Mendoza-Silva, E. Lohan, S. Trilles, M. Matey-Sanz, and J. Huerta, "A Comprehensive and Reproducible Comparison of Clustering and Optimization Rules in Wi-Fi Fingerprinting," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 769–782, 2022.
- [137] B. Jia, W. Qiao, Z. Zong, S. Liu, M. Hijji, J. Del Ser, and K. Muhammad, "A fingerprint-based localization algorithm based on LSTM and data expansion method for sparse samples," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 2022.
- [138] A. Brunello, A. Montanari, and N. Saccomanno, "A Framework for Indoor Positioning Including Building Topology," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 114 959–114 974, 2022.
- [139] A. Brunello, A. Montanari, and N. Saccomanno, "A genetic programming approach to WiFi fingerprint meta-distance learning," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 85, p. 101 681, 2022.
- [140] J. Cha and E. Lim, "A hierarchical auxiliary deep neural network architecture for large-scale indoor localization based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 120, 2022.
- [141] A. Panja, S. Karim, S. Neogy, and C. Chowdhury, "A novel feature based ensemble learning model for indoor localization of smartphone users," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 107, 2022.
- [142] L. Ma, Y. Zhang, and D. Qin, "A Novel Indoor Fingerprint Localization System Based on Distance Metric Learning and AP Selection," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, 2022.
- [143] P. Sadhukhan, K. Dahal, and P. K. Das, "A Novel Weighted Fusion based Efficient Clustering for Improved Wi-Fi Fingerprint Indoor Positioning," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2022.
- [144] A. Alitalishi, H. Jazayeriy, and J. Kazemitabar, "Affinity propagation clustering-aided two-label hierarchical extreme learning machine for Wi-Fi fingerprinting-based indoor positioning," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 13, no. 6, pp. 3303–3317, 2022.
- [145] M. Han and Y. Mao, "An Indoor Floor Location Method Based on Minimum Received Signal Strength (RSS) Dynamic Compensation and Multi Label Classification," in *The International Conference on Natural Computation, Fuzzy Systems and Knowledge Discovery*, Springer, 2022, pp. 584–591.
- [146] J. Chadha, A. Jain, and Y. Kumar, "Artificial intelligence techniques in wireless sensor networks for accurate localization of user in floor, building and indoor area," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 2022.
- [147] J. Yang, S. Deng, L. Xu, and W. Zhang, "Calibration-free 3D indoor positioning algorithms based on DNN and DIFF," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 15, p. 5891, 2022.
- [148] L. Wang, S. Tiku, and S. Pasricha, "CHISEL: Compression-Aware High-Accuracy Embedded Indoor Localization With Deep Learning," *IEEE Embedded Systems Letters*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 23–26, 2022.
- [149] Y. A. Ho, C. K. Tan, and Y. H. Ng, "Clustering indoor location data for social distancing and human mobility to combat covid-19," *Computers, Materials and Continua*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 907–924, 2022.
- [150] J. LIANG, Z. LIU, Z. ZHOU, and Y. XU, "Communication-efficient Federated Indoor Localization with Layerwise Swapping Training-Fed Avg," *IEICE Transactions on Fundamentals of Electronics, Communications and Computer Sciences*, 2022.

- [151] W. Njima, A. Bazzi, and M. Chaffi, "DNN-Based Indoor Localization Under Limited Dataset Using GANs and Semi-Supervised Learning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 69 896–69 909, 2022.
- [152] Q. Ye, H. Bie, K.-C. Li, X. Fan, L. Gong, X. He, and G. Fang, "EdgeLoc: A Robust and Real-Time Localization System Toward Heterogeneous IoT Devices," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3865–3876, 2022.
- [153] H. W. Khoo, Y. H. Ng, and C. K. Tan, "Enhanced Radio Map Interpolation Methods Based on Dimensionality Reduction and Clustering," *Electronics*, vol. 11, no. 16, p. 2581, 2022.
- [154] J. Park, J. Moon, T. Kim, P. Wu, T. Imbiriba, P. Closas, and S. Kim, "Federated Learning for Indoor Localization via Model Reliability with Dropout," *IEEE Communications Letters*, 2022.
- [155] X. Cheng, C. Ma, J. Li, H. Song, F. Shu, and J. Wang, "Federated Learning-Based Localization With Heterogeneous Fingerprint Database," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 11, no. 7, pp. 1364–1368, 2022.
- [156] S. Park, D. H. Kim, and C. You, "Fi-Vi: Large-Area Indoor Localization Scheme Combining ML/DL-Based Wireless Fingerprinting and Visual Positioning," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 127 094–127 116, 2022.
- [157] A. Sonny and A. Kumar, "Fingerprint Image-Based Multi-Building 3D Indoor Wi-Fi Localization Using Convolutional Neural Networks," in *2022 National Conference on Communications, NCC 2022*, 2022, pp. 106–111.
- [158] W. Shao, H. Luo, F. Zhao, H. Tian, J. Huang, and A. Crivello, "Floor Identification in Large-Scale Environments with Wi-Fi Autonomous Block Models," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 847–858, 2022.
- [159] S. Liu, R. de Lacerda, and J. Fiorina, "Hierarchical fingerprinting and feature extraction for indoor localization," in *2022 International Conference on Communications*, 2022.
- [160] H. Zhang and J. Xu, "Indoor Wi-Fi Fingerprint Localization Based on SDAE and MLP with Self-attention Mechanism," in *2022 China Automation Congress (CAC)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1963–1967.
- [161] A. Altamrah, W. Alasmay, J. Shuja, M. Alsaaban, and I. Ashraf, "Intelligent Positioning System: Learning Indoor Mobility Behavior and Batch Affiliations," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 122, no. 3, pp. 2521–2542, 2022.
- [162] D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, and J. Huerta, "Lightweight Hybrid CNN-ELM Model for Multi-building and Multi-floor Classification," in *2022 International Conference on Localization and GNSS, ICL-GNSS 2022 - Proceedings*, 2022.
- [163] A. T. Abraha and B. Wang, "MRILoc: Multiresolution Indoor Localization from crowdsourced samples," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 87, p. 101 719, 2022.
- [164] Y. Xu, Y. Zhao, Y. Yang, and D. Zhang, "Multi-floor Indoor Location Method Based on Fusion-CNN," in *2022 IEEE 14th International Conference on Wireless Communications and Signal Processing, WCSP 2022*, 2022, pp. 1064–1069.
- [165] H. Zhang, H. Fukunaga, R. Ishizuka, T. Li, and S. Tatenno, "Multi-floor Positioning Method based on RSSI in Wireless Sensor Networks," in *2022 61st Annual Conference of the Society of Instrument and Control Engineers (SICE)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 270–275.
- [166] Z. Tang, S. Li, K. Kim, and J. Smith, "Multi-Output Gaussian Process-Based Data Augmentation for Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Communications Workshops, ICC Workshops 2022*, 2022, pp. 361–366.
- [167] M. Laska and J. Blankenbach, "Multi-Task Neural Network for Position Estimation in Large-Scale Indoor Environments," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 26 024–26 032, 2022.
- [168] A. Fathalizadeh, V. Moghtadaiee, and M. Alishahi, "On the privacy protection of indoor location dataset using anonymization," *Computers and Security*, vol. 117, 2022.
- [169] J. Lu, C. Shan, K. Jin, X. Deng, S. Wang, Y. Wu, J. Li, and Y. Guo, "ONavi: Data-driven based Multi-sensor Fusion Positioning System in Indoor Environments," in *2022 IEEE 12th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8.
- [170] E. Ebaïd and K. Navaie, "Optimum NN Algorithms Parameters on the UJIIndoorLoc for Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Indoor Positioning Systems," in *2022 32nd International Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference (ITNAC)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 280–286.
- [171] S. Liu, R. de Lacerda, and J. Fiorina, "Performance analysis of adaptive K for weighted K-nearest neighbor based indoor positioning," in *IEEE 95th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC 2022-Spring)*, 2022.
- [172] Z. Wu, X. Wu, and Y. Long, "Prediction Based Semi-Supervised Online Personalized Federated Learning for Indoor Localization," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 10 640–10 654, 2022.
- [173] X. Cheng, T. Liu, F. Shu, C. Ma, J. Li, and J. Wang, *Providing Location Information at Edge Networks: A Federated Learning-Based Approach*, 2022.
- [174] M. Zecchin, S. Park, O. Simeone, M. Kountouris, and D. Gesbert, *Robust Bayesian Learning for Reliable Wireless AI: Framework and Applications*, 2022.
- [175] A. Pandey, R. Sequeira, and S. Kumar, "SELE: RSS-Based Siamese Embedding Location Estimator for a Dynamic IoT Environment," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3672–3683, 2022.
- [176] L. Klus, D. Quezada-Gaibor, J. Torres-Sospedra, E. Lohan, C. Granell, and J. Nurmi, "Towards Accelerated Localization Performance Across Indoor Positioning Datasets," in *2022 International Conference on Localization and GNSS, ICL-GNSS 2022 - Proceedings*, 2022.
- [177] X. Zhang, W. Sun, J. Zheng, M. Xue, C. Tang, and R. Zimmermann, "Towards Floor Identification and Pinpointing Position: A Multi-story Localization Model with WiFi Fingerprint," *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 1484–1499, 2022.
- [178] V.-H. Vu, B. Ngo-Van, and T. H. Do Thanh, "TWO-PHASE COMBINED MODEL TO IMPROVE THE ACCURACY OF INDOOR LOCATION FINGERPRINTING," *Journal of Computer Science and Cybernetics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 377–403, 2022.
- [179] N. Saccomanno, A. Brunello, and A. Montanari, "What You Sense is Not Where You are: On the Relationships between Fingerprints and Spatial Knowledge in Indoor Positioning," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 4951–4961, 2022.
- [180] A. Alitalehi, H. Jazayeriy, and J. Kazemitabar, "Wi-Fi fingerprinting-based floor detection using adaptive scaling and weighted autoencoder extreme learning machine," *Computer Science and Information Technologies*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 104–115, 2022.
- [181] C. Wu, W. Zhang, J. Yang, and S. Deng, "Wi-Fi indoor 3D localization algorithm based on multi-classifier fusion," *Engineering Research Express*, vol. 4, no. 3, p. 035 042, 2022.
- [182] K. Kostas, R. Y. Kostas, F. Zampella, and F. Alsehy, "WiFi Based Distance Estimation Using Supervised Machine Learning," in *2022 IEEE 12th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8.
- [183] Y. Wang, X. Gao, X. Dai, Y. Xia, and B. Hou, "WiFi Indoor Location Based on Area Segmentation," *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, vol. 22, no. 20, 2022.
- [184] N. Singh, S. Choe, R. Punmiya, and N. Kaur, "XGBLoc: XGBoost-Based Indoor Localization in Multi-Building Multi-Floor Environments," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 17, p. 6629, 2022.
- [185] O. Tasbaz, V. Moghtadaiee, and B. Farahani, "Zone-Based Federated Learning in Indoor Positioning," in *2022 12th International Conference on Computer and Knowledge Engineering (ICCKE)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 163–168.
- [186] X. Wu, M. Hu, and G. Dong, "A high available and strong generalization capability data-driven-based wireless fingerprint positioning model," in *2023 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Big Data and Algorithms (EEBDA)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1812–1819.
- [187] N. Agah, B. Evans, X. Meng, and H. Xu, "A Local Machine Learning Approach for Fingerprint-based Indoor Localization," in *Conference Proceedings - IEEE SOUTHEASTCON*, vol. 2023-April, 2023, pp. 240–245.
- [188] S. Ahdan, I. L. Putra, A. Sucipto, A. Suhartanto, E. A. Z. Hamidi, et al., "A Ranking-Based Feature Selection For Indoor Positioning System," in *2023 IEEE 9th International Conference on Computing, Engineering and Design (ICCED)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [189] C. Zhuang and D. Zhang, "A Robust WiFi Localization Algorithm Using Data Augmentation and Stacked Denoising Autoencoder," in *2023 35th Chinese Control and Decision Conference (CCDC)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1445–1450.

- [190] M. Jeong, S. W. Choi, and S. Kim, "A tutorial on Federated Learning methodology for indoor localization with non-IID fingerprint databases," *ICT Express*, 2023.
- [191] Y. Wang, L. Cheng, H. Yuan, and X. Li, "A WiFi Fingerprint Indoor Location Framework Based on Convolutional Neural Network," in *2023 International Conference on Intelligent Communication and Networking, ICN 2023*, 2023, pp. 34–37.
- [192] Y. Zhao, W. Gong, L. Li, B. Zhang, and C. Li, "An Efficient and Robust Fingerprint Based Localization Method for Multi Floor Indoor Environment," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2023.
- [193] A. Taneja, S. Rani, J. Breñosa, A. Tolba, and S. Kadry, "An improved WiFi sensing based indoor navigation with reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for 6G enabled IoT network and AI explainable use case," *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 149, pp. 294–303, 2023.
- [194] J. Xu, Z. Ning, Y. Zhou, X. Liao, W. Zou, and S. Xing, "An Indoor Localization Mechanisms Based on Local Differential Privacy," in *2023 4th Information Communication Technologies Conference (ICTC)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 121–126.
- [195] W. Long, X. Wen, and R. Zhu, "Demo Abstract: Real-Time 3D Indoor Localization with Multi-Dimensional RSSI on Mobile Robot," in *Proceedings of the 21st ACM Conference on Embedded Networked Sensor Systems*, 2023, pp. 490–491.
- [196] Y. Zhang, H. Du, J. Cao, G. Han, and D. Zheng, "DP-Loc: A Differential Privacy-Based Indoor Localization Scheme with Bilateral Privacy Protection," in *International Conference on Information Security and Cryptology*, Springer, 2023, pp. 293–304.
- [197] A. Alitalessi, H. Jazayeriy, and J. Kazemitabar, "EA-CNN: A smart indoor 3D positioning scheme based on Wi-Fi fingerprinting and deep learning," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 117, p. 105 509, 2023.
- [198] L. Klus, R. Klus, J. Torres-Sospedra, E. S. Lohan, C. Granell, and J. Nurmi, "EWok: Towards Efficient Multidimensional Compression of Indoor Positioning Datasets," *IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 3589–3604, 2023.
- [199] S. Li, Z. Tang, K. S. Kim, and J. S. Smith, "Exploiting Unlabeled RSSI Fingerprints in Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization through Deep Semi-Supervised Learning Based on Mean Teacher," in *2023 Eleventh International Symposium on Computing and Networking (CANDAR)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 155–160.
- [200] S. Yean, W. Goh, B.-S. Lee, and H. L. Oh, "extendGAN+: Transferable Data Augmentation Framework Using WGAN-GP for Data-Driven Indoor Localisation Model," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 9, p. 4402, 2023.
- [201] D. Kim and Y.-J. Suh, "GConvLoc: WiFi Fingerprinting-Based Indoor Localization Using Graph Convolutional Networks," *IEICE TRANSACTIONS on Information and Systems*, vol. 106, no. 4, pp. 570–574, 2023.
- [202] Y. Chen, G. Li, Y. Tan, and G. Zhang, "Graph-Based Radio Fingerprint Augmentation for Deep-Learning-Based Indoor Localization," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 6074–6084, 2023.
- [203] A. Brunello, A. Montanari, N. Saccomanno, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "High-Performance Features in Generalizable Fingerprint-Based Indoor Positioning," in *International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Systems: Computing, Networking, and Services*, Springer, 2023, pp. 46–67.
- [204] R. An, Z. Jing, Q. Zhou, and J. Mu, "Indoor Dual-indicator Precision Localization Network based on Multitask Learning," in *2023 IEEE International Symposium on Broadband Multimedia Systems and Broadcasting (BMSB)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [205] A. G. Putrada, N. Alamsyah, and M. N. Fauzan, "Indoor Keyless Entry Systems with Wi-Fi Fingerprint and Ensemble Learning Regression-Classification Model," *International Journal on Informatics Visualization*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 2206–2214, 2023.
- [206] R. Vishwakarma, R. B. Joshi, and S. Mishra, "IndoorGNN: A Graph Neural Network Based Approach for Indoor Localization Using WiFi RSSI," in *International Conference on Big Data Analytics*, Springer, 2023, pp. 150–165.
- [207] J. Torres-Sospedra, C. Pendão, I. Silva, F. Meneses, D. Quezada-Gaibor, R. Montoliu, A. Crivello, P. Barsocchi, A. Pérez-Navarro, and A. Moreira, "Let's Talk about k-NN for Indoor Positioning: Myths and Facts in RF-based Fingerprinting," in *2023 13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [208] Y. Mao, Z. Wu, and C. Tian, "Localization of Multi-Building Floors Based on Wavelet-CNN," in *Proceedings of the 2023 6th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Pattern Recognition*, 2023, pp. 373–380.
- [209] F. Pei, M. Shi, and X. Kong, "Multi-Level Feature Extraction and Autoregressive Prediction Based Wi-Fi Indoor Fingerprint Localization," in *Proceedings - 2023 China Automation Congress, CAC 2023*, 2023, pp. 1424–1428.
- [210] H. Zhu, L. Cheng, X. Li, and H. Yuan, "Neural-Network-Based Localization Method for Wi-Fi Fingerprint Indoor Localization," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 15, p. 6992, 2023.
- [211] J. Bi, M. Zhao, G. Yao, H. Cao, Y. Feng, H. Jiang, and D. Chai, "PSOSVRPos: WiFi indoor positioning using SVR optimized by PSO," *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 222, p. 119 778, 2023.
- [212] J. Torres-Sospedra, D. P. Quezada Gaibor, J. Nurmi, Y. Koucheryavy, E. S. Lohan, and J. Huerta, "Scalable and Efficient Clustering for Fingerprint-Based Positioning," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3484–3499, 2023.
- [213] T. Pham, N. Nguyen, T. Pham, and H. Bui, "Scalable Indoor Wi-Fi Positioning Algorithm Using Cluster-Based Local Estimators," in *2023 IEEE 8th International Conference on Recent Advances and Innovations in Engineering (ICRAIE)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [214] Q. Ye, X. Fan, H. Bie, D. Puthal, T. Wu, X. Song, and G. Fang, "SE-Loc: Security-Enhanced Indoor Localization with Semi-Supervised Deep Learning," *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 2964–2977, 2023.
- [215] T. Nagaraju and R. Murugeswari, "Self-attention-based multimodality convolutional volcano eruption network based indoor localization and wayfinding for blind people," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, pp. 1–24, 2023.
- [216] W. Zhuo, K. H. Chiu, J. Chen, J. Tan, E. Sumpena, S.-H. G. Chan, S. Ha, and C.-H. Lee, "Semi-supervised learning with network embedding on ambient rf signals for geofencing services," in *2023 IEEE 39th International Conference on Data Engineering (ICDE)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 2713–2726.
- [217] S. Li, K. S. Kim, Z. Tang, and J. S. Smith, "Stage-Wise and Hierarchical Training of Linked Deep Neural Networks for Large-Scale Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on Wi-Fi Fingerprinting," in *2023 Eleventh International Symposium on Computing and Networking Workshops (CANDARW)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 63–68.
- [218] B. Suleiman, A. Anaissi, Y. Xiao, W. Yaqub, A. S. Raju, and W. Alyassine, "Supervised Learning-Based Indoor Positioning System Using WiFi Fingerprints," in *International Conference on Advances in Computing Research*, Springer, 2023, pp. 56–71.
- [219] A. Brunello, A. Montanari, and N. Saccomanno, "Towards interpretability in fingerprint based indoor positioning: May attention be with us," *Expert Systems with Applications*, p. 120 679, 2023.
- [220] N. Saccomanno, A. Brunello, and A. Montanari, "Towards Learning an Optimal Metric for Fingerprint-based Localisation," in *Proceedings of the 29th Annual International Conference on Mobile Computing and Networking*, 2023, pp. 1–3.
- [221] C. Pendão, I. Silva, A. Moreira, F. J. Aranda, and J. Torres-Sospedra, "Towards Quality Wi-Fi Synthetic Data for Indoor Positioning Evaluation," in *2023 13th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–6.
- [222] Z. Yuan, F. Xu, S. Xu, and P. Tang, "Using Filtered Synthetic Data and Cluster K-Nearest Neighbor to Enhance the Accuracy of Fingerprint-Based Indoor Localization," in *2023 3rd International Conference on Electronic Information Engineering and Computer Science, EIECS 2023*, 2023, pp. 1215–1219.
- [223] M. Elkholy, H. Rizk, and M. Youssef, "Virtual Graph Neural Networks: A Novel Approach for Building-Agnostic Indoor Positioning System," in *Proceedings of the 31st ACM International Conference on Advances in Geographic Information Systems*, 2023, pp. 1–2.
- [224] Y. Yang, Q. Yang, T. Zhang, and W. Huang, "A Brownian Motion Restricted K-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm for Indoor Positioning," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 139, no. 1, pp. 625–651, 2024.
- [225] A. Shokry and M. Youssef, "A deployable quantum access points selection algorithm for large-scale localization," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.08943*, 2024.
- [226] M. Jan, W. Njima, and X. Zhang, "A Privacy-Preserving Indoor Localization System based on Hierarchical Federated Learning,"

- in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [227] F. Gu, F. Guo, F. Yu, X. Long, C. Chen, K. Liu, X. Hu, J. Shang, and S. Guo, “Accurate and efficient floor localization with scalable spiking graph neural networks,” *Satellite Navigation*, vol. 5, no. 1, 2024.
- [228] V. De Silva and C. Artaud, “Adversarial Contrastive Representation Learning for Passive WiFi Fingerprinting of Individuals,” in *2024 14th International Conference on Pattern Recognition Systems (ICPRS)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–7.
- [229] T. Zhao, X. Wang, S. Mao, S. Vucetic, and J. Wu, “Adversarial Machine Learning for Wireless Localization,” in *Network Security Empowered by Artificial Intelligence*, Springer, 2024, pp. 213–236.
- [230] J. Wang, Y. Tao, Y. Zhang, W. Liu, Y. Kong, S. Tan, R. Yan, and X. Liu, “Adversarial Examples Against WiFi Fingerprint-Based Localization in the Physical World,” *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 19, pp. 8457–8471, 2024.
- [231] A. Kargar-Barzi, E. Farahmand, N. T. Chatrudi, A. Mahani, and M. Shafique, “An Edge-based WiFi Fingerprinting Indoor Localization Using Convolutional Neural Network and Convolutional Auto-Encoder,” *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [232] Y. Zhao, W. Gong, L. Li, B. Zhang, and C. Li, “An Efficient and Robust Fingerprint-Based Localization Method for Multifloor Indoor Environment,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 3927–3941, 2024.
- [233] A. Raj, S. D. Shetty, and C. Rahul, “An efficient indoor localization for smartphone users: Hybrid metaheuristic optimization methodology,” *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 87, pp. 63–76, 2024.
- [234] Y. Zook, A. Shokry, and M. Youssef, “An Efficient Quantum Binary-Neuron Algorithm for Accurate Multi-Story Floor Localization,” in *2024 14th International Conference on Indoor Positioning and Indoor Navigation (IPIN)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [235] Z. Turgut and A. G. Kakisim, “An explainable hybrid deep learning architecture for WiFi-based indoor localization in Internet of Things environment,” *Future Generation Computer Systems*, vol. 151, pp. 196–213, 2024.
- [236] L. Royet, J. Torres-Sospedra, R. Montoliu, and A. Perez-Navarro, “Analysis of the origin of differences in position among different fingerprinting datasets,” in *2024 International Symposium on Sensing and Instrumentation in 5G and IoT Era, ISSI 2024*, 2024.
- [237] X. Shi, S. Fu, D. Yu, and M. Wu, “Asynchronous Federated Learning-Based Indoor Localization With Non-IID Data,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 21, pp. 35 113–35 125, 2024.
- [238] K. Long, Y. Li, K. Zhang, and X. Zhang, “Augmenting Multidimensional Fingerprint with Wavelet Transform for Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 2024.
- [239] R. Klus, J. Talvitie, J. Torres-Sospedra, D. Quezada-Gaibor, S. Casteleyn, D. Cabric, and M. Valkama, “C2R: A Novel Architecture for Boosting Indoor Positioning With Scarce Data,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2024.
- [240] M. I. Mahali, J.-S. Leu, N. A. S. Putro, S. W. Prakosa, and C. Avian, “DeepFuzzLoc Positioning: A Unified Fusion of Fuzzy Clustering and Deep Learning for Scalable Indoor Localization Using Wi-Fi RSSI,” in *2024 Joint 13th International Conference on Soft Computing and Intelligent Systems and 25th International Symposium on Advanced Intelligent Systems (SCIS&ISIS)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [241] N. Yoon, W. Jung, and H. Kim, “DeepRSSI: Generative Model for Fingerprint-Based Localization,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 66 196–66 213, 2024.
- [242] J. Machaj, C. Safon, S. Matúška, and P. Brída, “Detection of Access Point Spoofing in the Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Based Positioning,” *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 23, p. 7624, 2024.
- [243] A. K. Panja, S. Biswas, S. Neogy, and C. Chowdhury, “Dimensionality Reduction Through Multiple Convolutional Channels for RSS-Based Indoor Localization,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 22, pp. 37 482–37 491, 2024.
- [244] S. C. Narasimman and A. Alphones, “DumbLoc: Dumb Indoor Localization Framework Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 9, pp. 14 623–14 630, 2024.
- [245] J. Machaj, P. Brída, and B. Adamec, “Effect of Wi-Fi Access Points Spoofing on Fingerprinting Localization,” in *2024 34th International Conference Radioelektronika (RADIOELEKTRONIKA)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–5.
- [246] E. Boizard, G. Chardon, and F. Pascal, “Enhancing the Explainability of Gradient Boosting Classification Through Comparable Samples Selection,” in *2024 32nd European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 2027–2031.
- [247] G. Shen, Y. Sun, and F. Lu, “Enhancing Wi-Fi RSS-Based Indoor Positioning under Dynamic AP Availability: Leveraging Virtual Feature Maps and Contrastive Learning,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 17, pp. 27 902–27 913, 2024.
- [248] O. Kerdjadj, Y. Himeur, S. Atalla, A. Copiaco, A. Amira, F. Fadli, S. S. Sohail, W. Mansoor, A. Gawanmeh, and S. Miniaoui, “Exploiting 2-D Representations for Enhanced Indoor Localization: A Transfer Learning Approach,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 12, pp. 19 745–19 755, 2024.
- [249] F. Pei, M. Shi, and Y. Xie, “Federated Fingerprint Localization Method Based on Adaptive Aggregation and Feature Alignment,” *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, 2024.
- [250] J. Wang, J. Yang, B. Li, W. Meng, J. Zhang, and X. Zhang, “FEKNN: A Wi-Fi Indoor Localization Method Based on Feature Enhancement and KNN,” in *International Conference on Wireless Artificial Intelligent Computing Systems and Applications*, Springer, 2024, pp. 1–13.
- [251] Y. Etiabi, W. Njima, and E. M. Amhoud, “FeMLoc: Federated Meta-learning for Adaptive Wireless Indoor Localization Tasks in IoT Networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.11079*, 2024.
- [252] Z. Huang, B. Gao, and K. Xiong, “FGLNoRe: Federated Graph Learning on Non-IID RF Fingerprints for Building-Floor Positioning,” in *ICEIEC 2024 - Proceedings of 2024 IEEE 14th International Conference on Electronics Information and Emergency Communication*, 2024, pp. 16–20.
- [253] N. Agarwal, T. Sardana, and S. Bitragunta, “Gaussian Approximation-Based, Deep Neural Network-assisted Precise Indoor Localization,” in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Computing and Communication Technologies (CONECT)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–6.
- [254] S. Wang, S. Zhang, J. Ma, and O. A. Dobre, “Graph-Neural-Network-Based WiFi Indoor Localization System with Access Point Selection,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 20, pp. 33 550–33 564, 2024.
- [255] S. Li, K. S. Kim, Z. Tang, and J. S. Smith, “Hierarchical Stage-Wise Training of Linked Deep Neural Networks for Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization Based on Wi-Fi RSSI Fingerprinting,” *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 2024.
- [256] J. Torres-Sospedra, I. Silva, C. Pendão, F. Meneses, and A. Moreira, “Hyperparameterless k-NN for Wi-Fi Fingerprinting,” in *2024 International Conference on Localization and GNSS, ICL-GNSS 2024 - Proceedings*, 2024.
- [257] M. Nasir, K. Esguerra, I. Faye, T. B. Tang, M. Yahya, A. Tumian, and E. T. W. Ho, “HyTra: Hyperclass Transformer for WiFi Fingerprinting-based Indoor Localization,” *Transactions on Energy Systems and Engineering Applications*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–24, 2024.
- [258] M. Maduranga, H. Lakmal, V. Tilwari, W. Wanniarachchi, and W. Wijayarathne, “Improved 3D Wireless Indoor Localization with Deep Learning Algorithms,” *Signals and Communication Technology*, vol. Part F2556, pp. 211–222, 2024.
- [259] H. Esmaeili Gorjan and V. P. Gil Jiménez, “Improving Indoor WiFi Localization by Using Machine Learning Techniques,” *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 19, 2024.
- [260] A. K. Panja, S. F. Karim, S. Neogy, and C. Chowdhury, “Improving the sustainability of WiFi-enabled indoor localization systems through meta-heuristic based instance selection approach,” *Expert Systems with Applications*, vol. 257, 2024.
- [261] I. Neupane, S. Shahrestani, and C. Ruan, “Indoor Localization of Resource-Constrained IoT Devices Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting and Convolutional Neural Network,” in *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, 2024, pp. 20–25.
- [262] Y. Wang, Z. Zhao, F. Miao, Y. Xia, and H. Zhu, “Indoor Localization via Deep Learning with Self-Attention and Stacked Denoising Autoencoders,” in *Proceedings - 2024 International Conference on Interactive Intelligent Systems and Techniques, IIST 2024*, 2024, pp. 242–246.
- [263] H. Arslantas and S. Okdem, “Indoor Localization With an Autoencoder-Based Convolutional Neural Network,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 46 059–46 066, 2024.

- [264] M. Bayraktar, A. Ozcan, and U. D. Ulsar, "Indoor Localization with GravNetConv and Dynamic Graphs," in *2024 9th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 495–499.
- [265] L. Pan, H. Zhang, L. Zhang, R. Gao, and Q. Zhang, "Indoor positioning fingerprint database construction based on CSA-DBSCAN and RCVAE-GAN," *Physica Scripta*, vol. 99, no. 5, 2024.
- [266] J. Bi, J. Wang, H. Cao, G. Yao, Y. Wang, Z. Li, M. Sun, H. Yang, J. Zhen, and G. Zheng, "Inverse distance weight-assisted particle swarm optimized indoor localization," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 164, p. 112032, 2024.
- [267] Y. Chan, P.-Y. Lin, Y.-Y. Tseng, J.-J. Chen, and Y.-C. Tseng, "Learning-Based WiFi Fingerprint Inpainting via Generative Adversarial Networks," in *2024 33rd International Conference on Computer Communications and Networks (ICCCN)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–7.
- [268] H. Neyaz, M. Inamullah, and M. S. Beg, "Machine Learning Based Indoor Positioning System Using Wi-Fi Fingerprinting Dataset," in *International Conference on Electrical, Computer, and Energy Technologies, ICECET 2024*, 2024.
- [269] Y. Feng, Y. Wang, B. Zhao, J. Bi, and Y. Luo, "Machine Learning-Based WiFi Indoor Localization with FasterKAN: Optimizing Communication and Signal Accuracy," *Engineered Science*, vol. 31, p. 1289, 2024.
- [270] V. Moghtadaiee, A. Fathalizadeh, and M. Alishahi, "Membership Inference Attacks Against Indoor Location Models," in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Security and Cryptography*, 2024, pp. 584–591.
- [271] Y. Zhu, Y. Qiu, J. Wang, and F. Han, "Model Self-Supervised Federated Learning for Heterogeneous Fingerprint Localization," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 2250–2254, 2024.
- [272] Z. Tang, S. Li, K. S. Kim, and J. S. Smith, "Multi-Dimensional Wi-Fi Received Signal Strength Indicator Data Augmentation Based on Multi-Output Gaussian Process for Large-Scale Indoor Localization †," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 3, 2024.
- [273] S. Li, Z. Tang, K. S. Kim, and J. S. Smith, "On the Use and Construction of Wi-Fi Fingerprint Databases for Large-Scale Multi-Building and Multi-Floor Indoor Localization: A Case Study of the UJIIndoorLoc Database," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 12, p. 3827, 2024.
- [274] F. Dou, J. Lu, T. Zhu, and J. Bi, "On-Device Indoor Positioning: A Federated Reinforcement Learning Approach With Heterogeneous Devices," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 3909–3926, 2024.
- [275] Z. Wang, Y. Xu, Y. Yan, X. Ouyang, and B. Zhang, "Privacy-Preserving WiFi Localization Based on Inner Product Encryption in a Cloud Environment," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 17264–17282, 2024.
- [276] S. L. Ayinla, A. Abd Aziz, and M. Drieberg, "SALLoc: An Accurate Target Localization In Wifi-Enabled Indoor Environments Via Sae-Alstm," *IEEE Access*, 2024.
- [277] S. M. Nguyen, D. V. Le, and P. J. Havinga, "Seeing the world from its words: All-embracing Transformers for fingerprint-based indoor localization," *Pervasive and Mobile Computing*, vol. 100, p. 101912, 2024.
- [278] H. Sifaou and O. Simeone, "Semi-Supervised Learning via Cross-Prediction-Powered Inference for Wireless Systems," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.15415*, 2024.
- [279] M. Maduranga, H. Lakmal, and L. Kalansooriya, "Three-Dimensional Wireless Indoor Localization with Machine Learning Algorithms for Location-Based IoT Applications," *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 1995, pp. 1–12, 2024.
- [280] A. M. Da Rocha, G. N. De Oliveira, L. J. V. De Souza, and R. De Lacerda, "tLoc: A Mathematical Probabilistic Model for Wireless Fingerprinting," in *2024 32nd European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO)*, IEEE, 2024, pp. 2032–2036.
- [281] Q. Yan, W. Xiong, and H.-M. Wang, "TransGAN-Based Secure Indoor Localization Against Adversarial Attacks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 2024.
- [282] Q. Shen and Y. Cui, "WIFI Fingerprint Correction for Indoor Localization Based on Distance Metric Learning," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 24, no. 21, pp. 36167–36177, 2024.
- [283] P. Zhou, H. Wang, R. Gravina, and F. Sun, "WIO-EKF: Extended Kalman Filtering-Based Wi-Fi and Inertial Odometry Fusion Method for Indoor Localization," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 13, pp. 23592–23603, 2024.
- [284] J.-H. Park, D. Kim, and Y.-J. Suh, "WKNN-Based Wi-Fi Fingerprinting with Deep Distance Metric Learning via Siamese Triplet Network for Indoor Positioning," *Electronics (Switzerland)*, vol. 13, no. 22, 2024.
- [285] M. Abdalla, L. Alarabi, and A. Hendawi, "COVID-19 Contact Tracing Query Processing in IoT Using Spark," *Available at SSRN 4076712*, 2024.
- [286] M. A. Marins, R. S. Chaves, V. M. de Pinho, R. A. Cunha, and M. L. de Campos, "Tackling Fingerprinting Indoor Localization Using the LASSO and the Conjugate Gradient Algorithms."